

IMPROVEMENT OF THE UNIFIED MEDICAL INFORMATION AND ANALYTICAL SYSTEM FOR THE MATERIALS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7388692>

Annotation. In the modern process of globalization, various means of communication (ICT), including computers and the Internet, are widely used in all sectors of the economy. In turn, one of the most pressing issues is the creation of specific equipment for each service sector, production, science and special software systems that ensure the operation of this equipment. To date, our country has also achieved certain results in improving the results of optimizing the network of medical institutions, the formation of a modern system of medical care. Also, as a result of the activities carried out, the most relevant of them were identified.

Key words. Decree, contingent, single, medical, informational, analytical, system, improvement, mandatory, medical insurance, stage.

Relevance. As a result of the fact that the tasks and changes in the organizational and managerial system of health care are not fully covered by ICT, this negatively affects the ongoing changes, including the receipt and collection of information on the conduct of mandatory medical examinations of the population. population in electronic format, information and communication technologies with the ability to store, process, transmit and use information - the ICT system has not been created.

Maintaining and accepting large volumes of paper medical documents in the field does not allow to increase the efficiency and efficiency of the implementation of the necessary decisions and regulations, which leads to unnecessary bureaucratic actions. The above shortcomings do not allow predicting the growth of requirements for the quality of medical activities of the population. Therefore, the issue of training these specialists in the specifics of conducting mandatory medical examinations of the contingent of the contingent should be resolved - what level of specialist, the size of the reserve, the features of licensing and attestation and other similar issues. Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan is in the process of developing the state and society, raising the prestige of our country, improving the standard of living of the population in various fields. Such processes are reflected in the health care system.

The main source of funding for public health institutions is still the state budget. This process has a number of disadvantages in terms of efficient use of public resources.

Purpose of the study. In-depth study and analysis of the activities of the medical contingent of periodic medical examinations, improvement of a unified medical information and analytical system using information and communication technologies and the creation of a special program.

Research methods. The contingent for medical examination in Kibray district of Tashkent region. The main object is the staff of the district system of public education (2000), the staff of district medical institutions (2000). According to the Regulations on the medical

examination of workers [Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 29, 2012, Registration number No. 2387], the state of completeness of medical examinations and frequency of medical examinations by profession were studied. Quantitative and qualitative indicators of periodic medical examinations of the population of Kibray district of Tashkent region in district medical institutions, health care of the district, district medical association, health status of employees of medical institutions, morbidity, treatment, medical examinations and dynamics of medical care; state of medical records of contract contingents; the state of the electronic information system and information exchange in the district medical association.

Results and discussions of the study. The study includes an analysis of the current state of the organization of medical examination of population, the development of organizational and methodological measures to improve the system of medical examination of the population, and an assessment of effectiveness. It also describes the problems and ways of introducing interdepartmental integration systems for medical examination of population based on computer technology. Kibray district of Tashkent region is determined by its specificity, location, population and density, uniquely developed infrastructure, concentration of industry and other enterprises located in central socio-economic zone of the region.

As of 2020, the population of Kibray district is 202 thousand people, the economically active population is 150 thousand people. According to the State Tax Committee of the Kibray region, in 2020 the total number of enterprises and organizations operating in various forms of ownership is 3183, the total number of employees is 17733 people. Of these, the number of enterprises with a state budget and a state share is 82, and the total number of employees is 10,316 people. The number of private enterprises is 3,101 employing 7,417 people. On the territory of Kibray district of Tashkent region, there are 48 general educational institutions, where employ 2,553 teachers and employees of general secondary education work. Middle School No. 2 (IDUM) in Kibray City specializes in advanced English, school No. 6 specializes in mathematics, and schools No. 1, 16 and 30 specialize in specific sciences and foreign languages. Also, in Kibray region, there is 1 vocational school under the Department for the Development of Vocational Education, 3 secondary specialized educational institutions (academic lyceum at the Tashkent State Agrarian University, Chingeldin Professional College and Energy College). There are 83 food industry enterprises, 106 public catering facilities and 172 trade facilities in the Kibray region. 205 facilities administered by the Department of Public Hygiene, including:

- 31 hairdressers, 1 sauna, 4 dry cleaners;
- 182 multi-storey residential buildings, including 1 hostel;
- 1 sports institution;
- 4 resorts and sanatoriums;
- 1 treatment plant;- 53 medical institutions, including 11 public and 42 private medical institutions.

As a result of violation of sanitary and hygienic requirements or non-compliance with these requirements, these enterprises or their products may pose a danger to the population, because they are objects of epidemiological significance and their workers are traditionally called "maternity contingent". Hygiene education is required in accordance with current regulations. The third chapter of the dissertation entitled "Peculiarities of hygienic education

and training of the contingent of the contingent" is devoted to the analysis of the totality of factors of living conditions and lifestyle, the quality of medical care for the studied contingent.

The main documents regulating the organization and training of a contingent of contingents are:

- Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Health" (Article 17);
- Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 214);
- □ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Sanitary Supervision" (Article 18);
- □ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On sanitary and epidemiological welfare of the population" (Article 35);
- □ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On labor protection" (Article 17);
- □ Order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 200 dated July 10, 2012; Appendix 1 to the Order of the National Chamber of Innovative Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 3, 2019 No. 16 "Regulations on the organization of training the population in the minimum sanitary courses of the maternity group";
- □ Annex 3 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4790 dated July 27, 2020 "On the service of sanitary and epidemiological peace and public health of the Republic of Uzbekistan" (Chapter 2, paragraph 9). Network and regional programs "Health";
- □ Sanitary rules and norms for different types of production where the maternity contingent works;
- The following professions undergo hygienic training for the population of the maternity group at special courses:
 - workers in the production and sale of food products, including in medical institutions;
 - - workers of public services;
 - - Employees of schools, vocational colleges and lyceums, employees of preschool institutions, seasonal children's and adolescents' health institutions, camps and other children's health institutions agricultural workers in contact with food;
 - - employees of enterprises providing personal services to the population;
 - - Employees of pharmaceutical companies and pharmacies;

The current state of medical examination of the maternity contingent of the Kibray district of the Tashkent region to identify problems in the existing system of hygienic education of the descriptive contingent and groups, A sociological study was conducted in a total of 533 medical workers and 339 employees of general secondary education institutions related to the medical field to study opinions, suggestions and determine the degree satisfaction the level of hygienic preparation. were studied using a specially designed questionnaire, including the use of sociological research methods.

- According to a sociological survey of 533 employees of medical institutions of Kibray district of Tashkent region, there are 11 medical institutions in Kibray district of Tashkent region, of which 2260 medical workers work, including 1992 women and 268 men, as well as 49 educational institutions. educational institutions, of which 2,553 are staffed, of which 2,192 (85.86%) are women and 361 (14.14%) are men. The total number of nurses and doctors who filled out the questionnaire was 534 people, of which 60 were men and 474 were women, or 88.7% were women. Of the 2260 medical workers, 534 people, or 23.5%, were trained.

- The number of workers in general secondary education is 339, of which 22 are men (6.4%) and 317 are women, or 93.5% are women. In total, 339 out of 2553 employees of educational institutions were examined, which is 13.2%. The age classification of the examined medical personal is as follows: 345 people aged 18-44 years (65%), 174 people aged 45-60 years (32%) and 15 people aged 60-75 years (3%). A total of 534 people.
 - The age classification of the surveyed school teachers is as follows: 208 people aged 18-44 years (61.3%), 122 people aged 45-60 years (35.9%) and 9 people aged 60-75 years (2.6%). Total: 339 people.
 - The composition of the surveyed institutions was studied: KVP - 52 people, COP - 155 people, school - 1 person, CTMP - 184 people, CTTB - 168 people. at work.
 - 49 teachers of secondary schools of Kibray district were interviewed, in which 339 people work. Over the past 3 years, 154 (6%) of the total number of 2553 employees, 588 (23%) in 2019 and 798 (31%) in 2020, district medical associations were registered among employees of general educational institutions of general education. .
 - In 2019, the medical commission of Kibray District Medical Association examined only 4,992 employees or 4.3 percent (116,061) of the able-bodied population of Kibray District, of which 29 were diagnosed with certain diseases. Or only 0.58% of diagnosed diseases are women. According to general statistics, an average of 20% of the working population is employed in social services. As a result, the number of employed people should be 23 thousand people. It can be seen that only 21% of the population of the maternity group, subject to mandatory medical examination, covered 4992 people.
 - In 2019, when the district EMS studied the results of medical examinations of TTB employees, 43 employees of these institutions did not undergo timely medical examinations, and 40 employees received a serious warning "about passing medical examinations in a timely manner". Of the 873 surveyed respondents, 601 (68%) were physicians. The results of the examination, the conclusion of the medical commission, including information on the recommended treatment, but based on the nature of the identified diseases, in the prescribed manner, send employees to inpatient or sanatorium-resort treatment, as well as referrals to resorts, sanatoriums and preventive measures were not prescribed by the medical commission. 102 of a person (11%), the respondents believe that there are not enough narrow specialists in the composition of the medical commission. However, 192 (22%) employees had no information about transfer to an easier job by the employer for health reasons or without harmful and harmful consequences of production.
 - 452 people (51.7%) were not screened for breast cancer among women, and one of the main reasons was that 395 employees (45%) did not have the financial means to undergo an annual mammogram. In total, 822 (94%) employees knew about the timing of the re-examination, of which 52 (6%) were fined by the district DSES for late re-examination.
 - In addition, 187 workers (21%) had to undergo a medical examination at the "MUHR" in the "Personal Medical Book".
1. 829 employees (94%) who participated in the survey positively confirmed that it would be possible to simplify the submission of personal medical records and results of medical examinations in electronic form with a reminder of the time of passing a medical examination based on SMS notification. Thus, the analysis of the current state of the organization of hygienic education of the population, including the prevention of infectious and parasitic diseases, shows that it is necessary to develop a system of education (a unified

methodology) for hygienic education and education of highly qualified specialists, level of descriptive contingent in order to improve sanitation. Development of a comprehensive interdepartmental program for the protection and promotion of socially significant professions and their health based on the coordination of the activities of healthcare institutions, education and organizations, including three interrelated sections: informational, health and scientific.

Development of measures to attract teachers and leading specialists from nearby medical universities to organize medical examinations; Ensuring the organization and conduct of medical examinations, especially for women, the introduction of an expanded examination of specialists (mammologist); Early detection of diseases and their chronic forms through the organization of high-quality medical examinations and laboratory and instrumental studies, prevention and treatment of erats.

The introduction of electronic medicine on the "contingent", this system contributes to the organization of targeted and high-quality medical examinations using reliable information and statistics on a number of issues, such as when and in what specialty to conduct timely medical examinations, experts' opinions and recommendations, requirements and needs. In the fourth chapter of the dissertation entitled "Coverage of the population with comprehensive medical care", medical books and outpatient cards of teachers and district medical workers of the decisive contingent in the Kibray district of Tashkent region (1010) are considered.

Conclusions. The number of enterprises and employees of the Kibray region, which are required to undergo a mandatory medical examination, has been specified and their electronic register has been compiled for the region. According to the State Tax Committee of the Kibray region, in 2020 the total number of enterprises and organizations operating in various forms of ownership was 3,183, and the number of employees was 17,733 people. Insufficient implementation of information and communication technologies in the healthcare system, excessive document flow, excessive bureaucratization and high cost are factors affecting the completeness and accuracy of the medical examination of the contingent. Mandatory medical examinations have refined the scope and quality of medical examinations, as well as their accuracy. The program developed so far includes 1010 descriptive cohorts and evaluates the reliability of medical examinations conducted between them. An electronic analytical database has been created using ICT. An interdepartmental automated program for monitoring medical examinations of the maternal contingent has been developed and is being implemented. Ministry of Justice The Republic of Uzbekistan and the Agency for Intellectual Property issued certificates under the EKS program for medical examination of the contingent and the DC program for the medical examination of the contingent.

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